

CERTIFICATE OF APPRECIATION

THIS CERTIFIES THAT
TAFAKKUR MANZILI
JURNALIDA FAOL ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN

Muxanova Muyassar Gayratovna

THE FUNCTION OF DOWNLOADS IN A SENTENCE AND THEIR WRITING

NOMLI MAQOLASI BILAN ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN TAQDIRLANADI

2023/APREL

